

The Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in Regional Financial Management Board Aceh Besar

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Abstract: This study is to determine the effect of organizational culture, emotional intelligence and compensation on job satisfaction and employee performance. The object is the Regional Financial Management Board (BPKD) of Aceh Besar. The population in this study is all employees of BPKD of Aceh Besar, as much as 80 people distributed in various fields of work ranging from budget, accounting, income, treasury, fund transfer, secretariat and wealth. The sample is taken with purposive sampling that is only middle managers and staffs, as much as 78 respondents, excluding the 2 top leaders. Data analysis equipment uses Partial Least Square (PLS). The result shows that organizational culture influences job satisfaction significantly, organizational culture influences employee performance significantly, emotional Intelligence does not influence job satisfaction significantly, emotional Intelligence does not influence Employee Performance significantly, compensation influences job satisfaction significantly, compensation influences employee performance significantly, and job satisfaction influences employee performance significantly. The findings contribute to academic area that enrich the realm of knowledge, and to be a reference for the development of research model next. Also for the practical managers this can be a reference especially for BPKD of Aceh Besar to encourage its performance. The originality is also in the use of PLS as a statistic method. The limitation lies in the number of variables and an object.

Keywords: organizational culture, emotional intelligence, compensation, job satisfaction and employee performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization depends on individual employee performance. All institutions and companies will have goal to improve employee efficiency with the hope that it will be achieved by organizational goals. One way that is used by organizations to improve their employee performance, for example, is to improve organizational culture, to improve the emotional intelligence of employees and to give reward in return for the work results of their employees.

The Regional Financial Management Board (BPKD) of Aceh Besar District in realizing the Vision and Mission is carried out by all its employees. In its implementation, the Regional Financial Management Board is also supported by government work apparatus or regional / district work tool. At the district level, it is called BPKD as a District Work Unit. The BPKD of Aceh Besar consists of Head, Secretary, Head of Division, and Head of Sub-Division with a total of 80 civil servants.

The employee performance of BPKD of Aceh Besar is the work result in the quantity and quality which is produced by the state civil apparatus (ASN) in Regional Financial Management Board of Aceh Besar Regency based on responsibilities and task fields. Based on the results that are obtained by the author, it states that the employees in the Regional Financial Management Board of Aceh Besar District have not shown maximum performance as it is expected by the leaders.

The related phenomenon is that the performance of the state civil apparatus (ASN) in the BPKD of Aceh Besar District has not been maximized. It is inseparable from the influence of low quality, quantity and employee responsibility in carrying out their duties. The government administration management that has not been maximal yet

includes employee performance, and it is stated in Government Report of LHP BPK RI of 2017. In the LHP, it is explained that the performance of Aceh Besar employees is generally not optimal, including BPKD.

The phenomenon that still exists in BPKD of Aceh Besar as the object of this study is that the employee performance in the Regional Financial Management Board of Aceh Besar District is still not optimal from the quality of work that is produced, the quantity of work that can be completed, the low accuracy of work completion, the effectiveness of work time which has not achieved yet, the independence of employees in completing work, as well as the low work commitment of employees.

The employee performance that has not been maximized is determined by the factors of organizational culture, emotional intelligence, compensation and job satisfaction. The target of employee performance which has not been maximal yet is indicated by the factor in the level of job satisfaction that is felt by employees. Job satisfaction is a warm theme that is often questioned by management. In addition, the variables that influence the increase in job satisfaction and employee performance are related to the organizational culture that is owned by the employees in the Regional Financial Management Board (BPKD) of Aceh Besar. The phenomenon in this study is that the employee performance in BPKD of Aceh Besar has not been optimal yet from the quality of work which is produced, the quantity of work that can be completed, the accuracy of work completion time which that is still low, the effectiveness of work that has not been achieved, the employee independence in completing work, and the low work commitment of employees.

Several factors that cause low employee productivity are determined by organizational culture, emotional intelligence, compensation, and job satisfaction (Wibowo, 2012). The performance of the state civil apparatus (ASN) is still low. It is as a result of the factor of job satisfaction which is felt by employees. Job satisfaction is a theme that is often discussed in public sector management. This is seen from many indicators, such as employees who feel happy working in BPKD of Aceh Besar. There is mutual respect between work colleagues and the behavior which is shown by supervisors to employees, and the ability of employees to reduce workload.

(Bintoro&Daryanto, 2017) say culture is one of the main assumptions for learning and solving problems that exist within an organization. An organization that includes government bureaucracy is created as a forum to achieve a goal or several objectives. Organizational culture greatly influences productivity. In an organization, organizational culture is very important to achieve organizational goals. (Arianty, 2014) argues that organizational culture influences employee motivation and productivity. In addition, the factor of incompatibility with the work environment influences organizational culture. Employee commitment is important. Because the consequences include delays, absences, the desire to change jobs and staff changes.

Employee job satisfaction is inseparable from the lack of emotional intelligence from the employee himself. Employees with low emotional intelligence will always have impact on the level of job satisfaction that they feel. In addition, job satisfaction is also influenced by Compensation factors. The compensation is in the form of incentives. (Wibowo, 2012) says that in doing a particular job, someone expect the results or the rewards from the work that has been done. How much incentives which are given to employees will have direct impact on the level of satisfaction that they feel. Especially if the amount of incentives that are received by the employees exceeds their expectations, then the level of job satisfaction that they feel will be much greater.

(Wibowo, 2012) further says that compensation in the bureaucratic environment or public institutions is an interesting fact at any country including Indonesia. According to Hasibuan, high employee job satisfaction also has positive influence on overall employee performance. Job satisfaction is usually defined as the affective reaction of employees to jobs based on the comparison of desired results and actual results based on skills, experience and sincerity (emotional intelligence). The more satisfied the employee at work, the higher the work performance (Al-Ahmadi, 2009). The higher the employee performance, the more effective the performance will be.

II. LITERATURE

Employee Performance

(Wibowo, 2012) says that performance is not only a result of work or work achievement. But performance is how the work process goes. Performance is what is done and how to do it. Based on this understanding, the output that is produced by a state civil apparatus (ASN) is measured in his work and carried out in accordance with the competence which is possessed and the tasks that have been given.

Performance is the overall or output that is achieved by one institution. The performance of the state civil apparatus (ASN) is closely related to the achievement of the objectives of the organization. The state civil apparatus (ASN) performance cannot be free from the competency of existing human resources. The state civil apparatus (ASN) is a resource that is mobilized or run by officials who play an active role as actors in efforts to achieve organizational goals. This can be done well if there is attention to the performance of the apparatus.

Employee performance, according to (Siagian, 2012), is the overall ability/competence of a person to work so that the work goals can be achieved optimally and all targets that have been created with sacrifices are smaller on a scale compared to the obtained results.

Job Satisfaction

(Robbins & Judge, 2014) states that work satisfaction is a common attitude to one's work. It shows the consistency of expectations arising from the rewards that are given by his work. (Uha, 2013) job satisfaction is a feeling of the employee work, regardless of whether they are happy or not. It is as a result of the relationship between the apparatus and their environment or the notion of a mental attitude, as well as the results of employee evaluations. The employee feeling towards his job reflects his attitude and behavior at work.

Whereas according to (Davis & Newstrom, 1993), he suggests job satisfaction is the desire to support or not to support employees in activities. (Wexley & Yuki, 2005) provides a definition of job satisfaction, namely how employees feel themselves and their jobs.

The state civil apparatus (ASN) will be comfortable in carrying out his work if all components in the work and all elements within him support. And if that aspect does not support, the state civil apparatus (ASN) will feel the level of satisfaction is low. In line with the high IT development, in which all kinds of work equipment have been made by HR to make it easier and to save so that it can produce higher quality products. But HR still has a very big role because even though the equipment has been very modern, it can not operate yet and is only a dead tool and can be damaged if the HR does not expertise in operating it.

Organizational Culture

Opinion from (Robbins & Judge, 2014), organizational culture is a general perception from the members of organization. Organizational culture is a way of thinking and completing something that is inherited. It is used by all ASN employees and the ASN employees who have just learned or at least received part of this culture, who will be accepted as the members of organization. In fact, according to Kotter and Heskett, organizational culture is a value that is shared by all elements of the organization, more inclined to form the behavior of the group. Organizational culture, as a rule, is not visible, so it is so difficult to change. In this case, the norms of group behavior can be seen and reflected in the behavior model and organizational behavior about the change.

Based on some of the views above, it is concluded that organizational culture is a guide to ASN behavior. Confidence is obeyed and will be applied by ASN members. The problems that often arise in the ASN environment can be overcome with the help of basic assumptions and beliefs that are shared with ASN employees. The underlying assumptions and beliefs that ASN employees are compliant must be transferred to the ASN in the organization as a guide to their actions and behavior.

Emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman in (Nurita, 2012) "Emotional intelligence is an emotional skill that includes the ability to control one's self and has resistance in facing obstacle, be able to control the impulse and not to be satisfied quickly, manage his mood and be able to manage anxiety so that it will not disturb the ability to think, the ability to empathize and hope."

(Hein, 2007) in (Efendi & Sutanto, 2013) also state the idea of emotional intelligence that emotional intelligence is the potential for someone to feel, use, communicate, recognize, remind, describe, describe emotions. (Kerr, Garvin, Heaton, & Boyle, 2006) state that emotional intelligence is the ability to understand one's emotions and the other people's emotions to distinguish between them and use information to influence their thoughts and actions. argue that emotional intelligence leads to feelings and the ability of other people to recognize, the ability of self-motivating, and the ability to manage emotions well is one's self.

Compensation

Incentives are a form of compensation. It is how to provide motivation to employees to work optimally. Incentives are additional income in addition to salaries or wages which are given. The incentive is given so that employees can fulfill their needs.

From (Hasibuan, 2003), the definition of incentives is an additional gift which is given to certain employees whose achievements exceed standard performance. This incentive fee is a tool which is used to enforce the principle of justice in providing compensation. According to (Mangkunegara, 2010), the definition of incentives is the form of money which is granted by the leader of an organization to employees to work with motivation and high achievement in achieving organizational goals, to recognize the results of performance and the contribution from the employees.

From discussion above, the research model and hypothesis that can be formulate as follows.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

- H1 : organizational culture influences job satisfaction significantly
- H2 : organizational culture influences employee performance significantly
- H3 : emotional Intelligence influences job satisfaction significantly
- H4 : emotional Intelligence influences Employee Performance significantly
- H5 : compensation influences job satisfaction significantly
- H6 : compensation influences employee performance significantly
- H7 : job satisfaction influences employee performance significantly

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study is examined in the BPKD of Aceh Besar with the variables of research are organizational culture, emotional intelligence, compensation, job satisfaction and employee performance at the BPKD of Aceh Besar. The population in this study is all employees of BPKD of Aceh Besar, as much as 80 people distributed in various fields of work ranging from budget, accounting, income, treasury, fund transfer, secretariat and wealth. The sample is taken with purposive sampling that is only middle managers and staffs, as much as 78 respondents, excluding the 2 top leaders. Authors determine the constructs that is used for measuring the model, that are : 1) corporate culture : Leader behavior, organizational mission, Learning process, and Motivation; 2) emotional intelligence : Recognize self emotion, Manage your emotions, Motivate yourself, recognize the emotions of others, and build relationships; 3) compentation : performance, length of working, seniority, needs, fairness and appropriateness, and job evaluation; 4) job satisfaction : salary, the work itself, co-workers, boss, and promotion, and; 5) employee performance : quality of work, job knowledge, creativeness, cooperation, dependability, initiative, and personal qualities.

Data analysis equipment uses Partial Least Square (PLS) method. Partial Least Square is a way to predict in handling many independent variables, even though multicollinearity occurs between the variables (Alvi, Assad, Ramzan, & Khan, 2010). The PLS method of analysis has soft modeling because it is not based on the assumption that the data must be measured, the data is distributed free and the number of certain samples which means that the number of samples can be small (below 100 samples). PLS can be obtained on all types of data scales (nominal, ordinal, interval, ratio) as well as more flexible assumption requirements. It can also measure the relationship of each indicator to its construct. In addition, in the PLS a bootstrapping test can be performed on the structural model which is the outer model and inner model. It is decided to use PLS because this study uses indicators to measure each construct, and also the measurement model is structural.

IV. RESULT

The hypothesis tests that is conducted concludes the result as follows.

H1 is accepted : The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Job Satisfaction

Estimation in testing the relationship of organizational culture to employee job satisfaction results in CR score of 4.767 and significance level of 0.000. Both of them are obtained to accept H1 that the CR value is 4.767 which is greater

than 1.9991 and probability is 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. This indicates that the organizational culture influences the employee job satisfaction at the BPKD of Aceh Besar. This is in line with results that have proven from the previous research

H2 is accepted : The Influence of organizational culture on Employee Performance

Estimation in testing the relationship of organizational culture with employee performance shows the score of the original sample estimation of CR at 3.443 and the significance at 0.001. All the obtained values are the conditions for accepting H2. The CR score at 3.443 is larger than 1.9991 and the significance at 0.001 is smaller than 0.05. It means that the existing organizational culture influences the employee performance at BPKD of Aceh Besar. This is in line with results that have proven from the previous research.

H3 is rejected : The Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Job Satisfaction

The estimation in testing the influence of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction is that CR value at 1.402 and significance at 0.162. The two produced values cannot be made as the condition for accepting H3. The CR score at 1.402 is smaller than 1.991 and significance at 0.162 is more than 0.05. It means that emotional intelligence does not influence the employee job satisfaction at BPKD of Aceh Besar. This result is in line with Nicholas Simarmata et al (2004) that proves there is a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence with job satisfaction in improving performance. This result argues the previous ones that have proven from another researcher. This means that emotional intelligence is not one of the factors that need to be fixed in BPKD of Aceh Besar.

H4 is rejected : The Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance

Testing the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee performance shows the score of the original sample estimation value of CR at 1.347 and with probability at 0.179. The two generated values cannot be used for accepting H4 conditions. The CR value at 1.347 is not greater than 1.991 and the probability is smaller than 0.179. It can be explained that the emotional intelligence which is possessed by employees does not influence the employee performance at BPKD of Aceh Besar. This result argues the previous ones that have proven from another researcher. This means that emotional intelligence is not one of the factors that need to be fixed in BPKD of Aceh Besar.

H5 is accepted : The Influence of Compensation on Job Satisfaction

In testing the influence of estimated compensation on employee job satisfaction, it is obtained that the original sample estimation of CR value at 5.999 and significance at 0.000. This is the condition for accepting H5. The CR value at 5.999 is greater than 1.991 and a probability at 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. It indicates that compensation influences employee job satisfaction at BPKD of Aceh Besar. This is in line with results that have proven from the previous research.

H6 is accepted : The Influence of compensation on employee performance

Estimation for testing the influence of compensation on employee performance obtains an original sample estimation value of CR at 4.499 and significance at 0.000. The two values meet the requirements for accepting H6. The CR value at 4.499 is greater than 1.991 and probability at 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. It means that compensation influences the employee performance of the Regional Financial Management Board in Aceh Besar District. This result is in line with (Fatima Mamdani&Minhaj, 2016) who prove that the higher the level of incentives, the better the employee's performance.

H7 is accepted : The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Estimation on testing the relationship of job satisfaction to employee performance obtains the original sample estimation of CR at 2.412 with significance at 0.016. This fulfills the requirements for accepting H7. The CR at 2.412 is greater than 1.991 and the probability at 0.016 is smaller than 0.05. It means that job satisfaction influences the employee performance at BPKD of Aceh Besar. This is in line with the research conducted by (Simarmata, 2013) who say that there is a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence with job satisfaction in improving performance.

These all hypothesis test results figure the condition of BPKD of Aceh Besar related to the variables. The influences among variables can be the map of the problem and the evaluation will provide the strategic decision to increase the employee performance.

CONCLUSION

The result shows that organizational culture influences job satisfaction significantly, organizational culture influences employee performance significantly, emotional Intelligence does not influence job satisfaction significantly, emotional Intelligence does not influence Employee Performance significantly, compensation influences job satisfaction significantly, compensation influences employee performance significantly, and job satisfaction influences employee performance significantly. The findings contribute to academic area that enrich the realm of knowledge, and to be a reference for the development of research model next. Also for the practical managers this can be a reference especially for BPKD of Aceh Besar to encourage its performance. The originality is also in the use of PLS as a statistic method. The limitation lies in the number of variables and an object.

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